

РОЛЬ ЦИФРОВИЗАЦИИ В БУХГАЛТЕРСКОМ УЧЁТЕ**Утемуратова М.П.***старший преподаватель кафедры «Финансы и бизнес-аналитика»,
Ташкентский государственный экономический университет***THE ROLE OF DIGITALIZATION IN ACCOUNTING****Utemuratova M.***senior lecturer at the department of «Finance and Business Analytics»,
Tashkent State University of Economics***Аннотация**

В статье рассмотрен вопрос о необходимости цифровизация в бухгалтерском учёте. Даны перспективы применения цифровых технологий, как ускоренный фактор анализа бухгалтерской деятельности, способствующий оптимизации взаимодействия предпринимателей на основе создания единого пространства данных. Также, предложены дополнительные методы внедрения цифровизации в бухгалтерию, позволяющий ускорить работу и быстрому принятию решения в бизнесе.

Abstract

The article considers the issue of the need for digitalization in accounting. The prospects for the use of digital technologies are given as an accelerated factor in the analysis of accounting activities, contributing to the optimization of the interaction of entrepreneurs based on the creation of a single data space. Also, additional methods for introducing digitalization into accounting have been proposed, which allows speeding up work and quick decision-making in business.

Ключевые слова: блокчейн, бухгалтерский учёт, цифровые технологии, искусственный интеллект, машинное оборудование.

Keywords: blockchain, accounting, digital technologies, artificial intelligence, machinery.

Introduction.

The use of digital technologies in accounting will contribute to the further development of automation of a large number of functions; maximum simplification of any processes; improving operational efficiency and transparency of actions taken; simplification of transactions for international business. In the conditions of the digital economy, the undoubted advantages in making managerial decisions are that the heads of economic entities have the opportunity to receive large amounts of information in the required sections in the shortest possible time. Modern accounting is an information base on the basis of which business entities prepare financial statements[1]. Such reporting characterizes the financial position and financial result of the activity of an economic entity (profit or loss). In addition, it provides systematic control of the correctness and accuracy of accounting data at the end of each accounting cycle.

The digitalization of accounting will develop and increase in all areas of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Moreover, new tools will appear, updated software, the list of functions of which will only expand. Thus, digital processes have great prospects in accounting.

Theoretical aspects of research work.

In modern conditions, the process of implementing innovations in accounting is associated with the use of computer technology and information and communication technologies. This reveals one of the most important properties of informatization - its universalism and all-pervasive ability as a toolkit that provides processes for improving management and supporting management systems at a high level of efficiency[2]. The purpose of information support of any process is to obtain processed information based on the collected initial data, which should serve as the basis for making managerial decisions. To achieve this goal, it is necessary to solve a number of particular tasks, such as collecting primary information, storing it, distributing it between the structural divisions of the enterprise and their employees, preparing for processing, processing itself, providing the management body in a processed form, analysis, providing direct and feedback links in its circulation, etc.

Currently, electronic document management systems are becoming increasingly popular in management information support, which allow:

Fig.1. Electronic document management systems[3]

With modern information flows, an effective solution of these problems is impossible without the use of computer technology and new information technologies.

The digitalization of accounting has a significant impact on two of its points (Fig. 1):

1. The technology of accumulating (receiving) the necessary information, storing it, and subsequently

transferring it to interested users - information technologies in accounting[4]. Technology is understood as modern information systems, which are carried out through the formation and maintenance of databases. Information systems are developing in the context of two components: the development of technology (the creation of a new technical base) and the improvement of automated information systems (AIS).

Fig.2. The impact of digitalization on aspects of accounting[5]

2. Methodologies for systematizing information, that is, the essence of accounting or accounting methodology), by means of binary notation, as a result of which it becomes possible to use more than two accounts.

By increasing the accounting accounts, sub-accounts of analytical accounts, management information accounts, it can be systematized, generalized and presented to interested users in the most detailed, analytical and convenient format, which cannot be done with manual data processing. All these changes are prerequisites for the creation of triple instant accounting, and in the future, stereo accounting.

The concept of stereo accounting was introduced by I.R. Sukharev, its purpose is the formation of financial statements at any time, and not within the established time frame of a month, quarter, year[6]. This requires a clear division of accounting accounts into static ("moment") and dynamic ("interval"). Such a distinction allows the formation of a full-fledged dynamic equality, similar to the static balance of assets and liabilities. The classic double entry is modified so that it is no longer possible to capture the full variety of quantifiable indicators of a company's financial statements, including any disclosures. In connection with this, the differences between the entry in the accounting account

and the entry in the reporting line are erased. This approach reduces the cost and time of preparing financial statements online as the primary information is entered.

Analyze and result of research work.

Digitalization is an approach to the use of digital resources in the work of an organization. It involves the redefinition of technologies and business processes to improve the working environment of employees, interaction with customers and other participants in the modern enterprise. Digitization improves company productivity and is one of the top priorities for business leaders and IT organizations around the world.

The trend of digitalization of the modern economy involves the modification of approaches to doing business[7][8]. Given the further increase in competition in the market, top managers of corporations are betting on new technologies and the introduction of innovations, as a result of which it becomes relevant to study the essence and possibilities of using block chain technology, artificial intelligence, machine learning in accounting and business entity management, thanks to which it is possible to develop a unified information space, equally interpreted by all stakeholders.

The study of the evolution of the development of the use of information technologies in accounting made it possible to single out the following stages: the use of

Microsoft Excel spreadsheets, the introduction of specialized software products, the use of integrated ERP enterprise management systems and cloud technologies. Excel spreadsheets allow you to systematize the available information according to the required criteria, generate totals, select the necessary information by creating separate tables, and consolidate information from several files into one.

ERP enterprise management systems allow, in conditions of complex production, an extensive branch network, a large assortment of products and an increased volume of warehouse operations, to combine several tasks: to combine all business processes according to uniform rules within one system; promptly receive information about all aspects of the enterprise; plan and control the activities of the organization.

The processing and storage of information on the Internet - "cloud technologies" - is another modern direction in accounting automation. Undoubtedly, it has a number of advantages: no initial investment is required, easy access, no restrictions on users. At the same time, the following shortcomings are inherent in existing accounting technologies[9]:

- risks of loss and distortion of information;
- fragmentation and poor quality of data;
- the lack of the possibility of automated formation of accounting and analytical information, taking into account the time value of money;
- focus on the needs of existing accounting methods;
- lack of integration into the international accounting system.

A new stage in the development of information technologies - artificial intelligence, machine learning, block chain technology - will level these problems. In the last decade, the number of companies that are implementing the concept of digital transformation has increased, which includes not only the use of new technologies (for example, machine learning, artificial intelligence applications, the Internet of things, block chain), but also changes in key business elements, including strategy, business model, business processes.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is primarily machine learning. The goal of this concept is to create programs that can independently analyze data, make decisions, create concepts and learn based on given rules, without the use of additional programming. Using statistical methods and econometric models, artificial intelligence can build forecasts and scenarios for the development of events, process an array of unstructured data into useful information, and adjust its actions taking into account changing business conditions.

Machine learning (from English - machine learning) - algorithms that allow a computer to draw conclusions based on data without following certain rules. Its goal is to partially or completely automate the solution of complex professional problems, and the scope of machine learning is constantly expanding. The use of machine learning provides unlimited opportunities in making managerial decisions: by means of in-depth analysis, it is possible to identify and predict further developments related to maximizing profits and reducing costs. The use of machine learning allows you to optimally use the capital and funds of the company, reduce risks, increase market stability and efficiency.

At the same time, the block chain forms a space that allows all market participants to unambiguously evaluate information, and artificial intelligence allows for the multivariance of reports, taking into account risks. Innovative technology allows records to be stored on a public system that provides secure access to auditors and third parties.

Conclusion.

Generalization and analysis of the results of the study show that in connection with the opening opportunities, the use of digital technologies in accounting will contribute to the further development of:

automation of a large number of functions; application of cryptographic protection for accounting records;

firms will not need to resort to the services of intermediaries to check all their documents; maximum simplification of any processes;

improving operational efficiency and transparency of actions taken;

simplification of transactions for international business.

In the conditions of the digital economy, the undoubted advantages in making managerial decisions are that the heads of business entities have the opportunity to receive large amounts of information in the required sections in the shortest possible time.

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